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Medibot: Enhancing Healthcare Delivery in Undeveloped Regions through Human-Assisted Robot

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ABSTRACT

The rapid advancements in science and technology over the past century have significantly improved medical science, yet these benefits remain unevenly distributed, particularly in underdeveloped regions. Poor infrastructure, narrow roads, and limited resources in these areas hinder effective healthcare delivery. Global outbreaks like COVID-19 have exposed systemic weaknesses in existing healthcare systems, especially in underdeveloped countries. Although semi-autonomous robots show promise for enhancing healthcare delivery, current solutions are often expensive, complex, and unsuitable for harsh environments. This study introduces Medibot, a cost-effective, semi-autonomous four-wheeled robot equipped with a 5 Degrees of Freedom (DoF) arm, designed to address these challenges. Medibot's compact and robust design enables navigation in narrow and rough terrains, making it suitable for underserved regions. It supports both manual and autonomous operation via a smartphone app, featuring obstacle detection, video feed, and an LCD for patient-doctor communication. Medibot facilitates medical supply transport, sample collection, and symptom documentation while minimizing disease transmission during outbreaks. Experimental results validated Medibot's accuracy in obstacle detection and navigation, achieving a mean error of under 5% in obstacle distance measurements. The robot arm demonstrated high precision with a mean error of under 2cm in reaching target coordinates. Medibot's total production cost is only \$120, making it an affordable solution for widespread implementation in underdeveloped regions. Overall, Medibot presents a cost-effective solution with the potential to enhance healthcare accessibility, curb disease transmission, and meet rising medical demands in resource-limited settings.

KEYWORDS: Robotics, Healthcare, Contagious Disease, Automation

1. INTRODUCTION

In the past century, rapid development in science and technology has significantly transformed medical science, leading to increased life expectancy, more effective pharmaceuticals, and cures for previously incurable diseases. However, these advancements have not benefited everyone equally. Urban areas, which are often the epicenters of technological innovations, are marked by stark contrasts between the living standards of the affluent and the underprivileged communities [1]. While citizens of affluent areas enjoy advanced healthcare services, those living in poorer and slum areas often face neglect. The infrastructures of these underdeveloped areas are characterized by unplanned housing and narrow roads, which pose significant hindrances to medical delivery services [2].

Additionally, recent global outbreaks of contagious diseases such as Covid-19 and SARS have further pointed to the shortcomings of the existing healthcare delivery system. A scarce supply of skilled manpower and Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) led to poor healthcare delivery services in underdeveloped countries during these outbreaks [3].

Several previous studies have explored the potential of using semi-autonomous robots to alleviate shortcomings faced in medical delivery and healthcare. Chen et al. [4] discusses the potential of using self-driving robots for end-product delivery to minimize transmission of contagious diseases like COVID-19. Another study by Khamis et al. [5] proposes the automation of sample collection and management of contagious diseases to

enhance healthcare service. Similarly, Khan et al. [6] explored the role of semi-autonomous robots in various healthcare sectors, particularly in mitigating disease outbreaks. The use of automation for Covid sampling was also proposed [7]. Another study [8] suggested the implementation of Mobile Clinics for better healthcare accessibility. Additionally, Nyaaba et al. [9] proposed the use of drones to deliver healthcare products in emergencies in Africa, aiming to reduce delivery time and make transportation more efficient.

Despite the promising advancements in robot-assisted healthcare delivery systems, many of the existing solutions are complex, expensive and only suitable for specific settings. Most of these specialized robots are often too large for navigating in the narrow, unplanned environments of lower-income regions. Moreover, they require certain infrastructures to support full functionalities, like high bandwidth internet connection, not widely available in underdeveloped regions. These machines also require special technical expertise which is limited in lower-income regions. Additionally, the cost of production and maintenance of these complex robots are often too high for lower income regions to implement them on a large scale. These limitations have created a gap in medical care delivery service robots that can function reliably in underdeveloped regions.

The aim of this study is to address the gaps faced in healthcare delivery services in underdeveloped countries by proposing a viable solution combining technology and practicality. The primary concerns were the unplanned residencies of the slum areas which are hard to navigate due to their narrow and poor-quality roads. Another concern was the affordability of the solution. As it's aimed at underdeveloped countries, widespread implementation would require affordable production and upkeep costs. Ease of use was a priority as specialized training facilities are scant in underdeveloped countries. It also had to contain all the necessary equipment and functionalities suited for remote medical service. Lastly it had to be able to adapt to the harsh environment and function properly with the limited infrastructure of these regions.

Figure 1: Prototype of Medibot

This paper introduces Medibot, a promising solution to address the limitations faced in healthcare delivery services in underdeveloped countries. It is a cost-effective, semi-autonomous four-wheeled robot equipped with a 5 Degrees of Freedom (DoF) arm. It aims to address the gaps by integrating the insights of the previous studies and combining newer and more affordable technologies. Its small but versatile form factor enables it to transport medical supplies through narrow and rough roads in remote and underserved areas, collect patient samples, and document symptoms. While it's easy to procure parts and ease of use ensures easy widespread adoption.

The Medibot can be remotely operated through a smartphone app. The app enables manual control of both the wheels and the arm of the robot, while also providing video feed to assist with navigation. The robot also supports automatic navigation enabled by obstacle detection via sonar module. The camera module can also be equipped with an object detection algorithm to enhance maneuverability. For arm movement precision, inverse kinematics was incorporated. To facilitate communication between the patients and the doctors, the bot is equipped with an LCD. Patients can submit their disease symptoms through a QR code displayed on the chassis of the robot, which is linked to a form database. Medibot is also designed to facilitate carrying sample collection tubes for gathering the bodily fluids of patients, which can be later analyzed in laboratories for diagnosing diseases. Furthermore, during outbreaks, it can play a crucial role in providing valuable healthcare services while reducing transmission of diseases since direct human contact can be avoided using it.

2. METHODOLOGY

An Arduino Uno acts as the brain of Medibot, which is wired to necessary components and programmed accordingly to carry out all the functionalities smoothly. To aid mobility of the robot, it is wired to four DC motors via L293D motor driver. The motor driver relays the speed and direction of rotation instructions from the Arduino to the DC motors, which are linked to the wheels. To provide automatic navigation functionality, obstacle detection is implemented. It employs a SR-04 Ultrasonic sensor to calculate distance of obstacles and sends the data back to the Arduino. Which then takes optimal direction based on preprogrammed logics. For arm joint movement, four servo motors are connected to the Arduino via Digital I/O ports. Inverse Kinematics is incorporated to increase accuracy of arm movement. To facilitate patient and doctor communication, an LCD equipped with I2c module is connected to the Arduino digital port. A Sonar is also connected to the Arduino for autonomous navigation purposes and mounted on a motor, allowing it to rotate and extend the object detection range. To enable precise remote control of the robot, a video feed stream is provided by the ESP32 camera and Wi-Fi module. Lastly, to provide user input and enable manual control, an HC-05 Bluetooth module is connected to the serial ports of the Arduino. A smartphone app developed by MITappinventor [10] is used for abridging Arduino and user communication. The overall framework of Medibot along with its functionalities is shown in Fig.2.

The 3D model of Medibot was developed using SOLIDWORKS [11], while its circuit diagram was developed using Proteus [12]. The circuit diagram of Medibot has been displayed in Fig. 3.

Figure 2: Framework of Medibot

Figure 3: Circuit Diagram of Medibot

The design enables Medibot with its key functionalities which can be categorized as 1) Semi-Autonomous navigation 2) Auto-navigating arm and 3) Interactive usability

2.1. Semi-autonomous navigation

To add Autonomous functions to its navigation, Medibot uses a Sonar sensor. The sensor measures the distance of objects from the robot and sends out the reading to Arduino. Medibot has two modes of Autonomous navigation: i) Follow mode and ii) Self-driving mode. Besides Autonomous navigation, it can also be controlled remotely using a smartphone application. Block diagram of the autonomous navigation process can be seen in **Fig. 4**.

When Medibot is in “Follow mode”, it maintains a predefined distance between itself and the object or person it is following. This function is useful when it needs to follow a guide to its destination. “Self-driving mode” is a fully autonomous mode where it does obstacle detection and moves forward avoiding the obstacles.

Figure 4: Block Diagram of the Autonomous Navigation Process

The principles of Sonar:

By application of I/O Trigger Ranging, the high-level signal is maintained for 15µs at least, at a frequency of 40 KHz in the form of a square wave. When turned on, the high-level signal is produced, and the return signal is detected. The duration between the launch and return of the high-level signal is the time(t) measured. The formula for calculating obstacle distance(s) is denoted by,

$$s = v_a * \frac{t}{2} \tag{1}$$

Where V_a is the velocity of sound in air.

The velocity of sound in air depends on its thermodynamic properties such as temperature, atmospheric pressure, and humidity level. The velocity of sound in air is typically assumed to be 340m/s for calculations.

Figure 5: Operating Principle of the Sonar Sensor

There are some limitations faced in measuring distance using ultrasonic sensors. When the obstacle is perpendicular to the waves transmitted, accurate distance can be measured as depicted in **Fig. 5**. However, if the obstacle is at an angle to the Sonar Module, only a few waves reflect off the obstacle. Making the distance measurement erroneous. Mounting the sensor on a servo motor can solve this issue and extend the angle of detection. The sensor used in Medibot is HC-SR04. To increase the detection range, a servomotor has been used as can be seen in **Fig. 6**. The sensor has an effective range of 30 degrees from the vertical on both sides. The range has been extended by mounting it on a servo motor.

Figure 6: Sonar sensor mounted on servo motor working at different angles

2.2. Auto-navigating Arm

Medibot is equipped with a 5 Degrees of Freedom Arm which is powered by 3 servomotors for the links and one Servomotor for the gripper. Controlling the Arm by controlling the individual motors is quite time-consuming and less precise. To solve this issue, Inverse Kinematics is used in the Medibot. Kinematics is the study of motion without explicit focus on the forces behind the motion. Inverse Kinematics in Robotics is concerned with the process of calculating the angles needed by the joints of a kinematic chain to get the end effector to a particular location and orientation. To solve the angles required for a particular end effector location, some constraints need to be stated first, which adjust the workspace boundary of the arms reach. The constraints are the angular range of the servomotors used, and the length of the links used in the arm. Block diagram of inverse kinematics mechanism has been presented in **Fig. 7**.

Figure 7: Mechanism of Inverse Kinematics

Inverse Kinematics is solved by combining the use of Pythagoras law and trigonometric rules. The schematic of the Robot Arm can be seen in **Fig. 8**. The planar axes are denoted as the x-axis and y-axis while the vertical axis is designated as the z axis. AA' represents the base link of the robot arm, which rotates about the horizontal plane at θ_1 angle to the x-axis. AB denotes the shoulder link, which moves at an angle of θ_2 relative to the horizontal. Similarly, BC denotes the arm link, which also moves at an angle of θ_3 with respect to the horizontal.

Figure 8: Schematic Representation of Robot Arm ABC

To determine the desired degree of rotation of the base joint, the tangent formula can be used,

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1}\left[\frac{y}{x}\right] \tag{2}$$

Where (x, y, z) is the desired location of the end effector.

To measure the angles of the shoulder and arm joint, the Pythagorean theorem and the rule of the cosine are simultaneously applied to the joints.

$$C = \sqrt{A^2 + B^2} \tag{3}$$

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{A^2+B^2-C^2}{2AB}\right) \tag{4}$$

The calculated angles of link joints are then applied to the Servomotors for the desired end-effector location.

2.3. Interactive usability

The interactive usability of Medibot is facilitated by a smartphone application developed using MITappinventor [10]. This app allows manual control of the bot, including precise movement of its wheels and robotic arm. Automatic navigation can be enabled or disabled from the app. It can also toggle the LCD, Sonar module, Camera Module on-off. Each functionality is linked to an interactive button within the app, which when pressed, generates a specific alphanumeric command. These commands are transmitted to the Arduino Uno via the serial bus using Bluetooth communication. Each command contains two parts. The initial part contains the unique

identifier corresponding to the targeted component. The rest is the value for the specified operation. Upon receiving a command from the app, the Arduino processes it by first analyzing the destination of it, then executes the instruction. To optimize control and enhance error monitoring, the Arduino is configured to send logs of all instructions executed to the smartphone app's terminal. If an invalid command is provided by the app, Arduino is programmed to reject the command. Predefined limits for each component were determined through experimentation and incorporated into the Arduino's programming. An emergency stop feature is also integrated into the app, allowing users to immediately halt all functionalities of the Medibot if necessary. A simplified control flow diagram of the smartphone app can be seen in Fig. 9.

Figure 9: Interactive Functionalities of Medibot

3. DATA COLLECTION

3.1. Coordinate Testing

The purpose of this test is to measure the accuracy of the robot arm in reaching the destination coordinates. The test is carried out by using a coordinate board and a ruler. The results of the coordinate test is shown in Fig. 10. From the results of the coordinate testing, it is found that the end effector managed to reach the destined coordinate with some associated error. The largest mean error occurred in the X axis, at 17mm, while the smallest mean error occurred in the Z axis, at 6.6mm. When looking at individual tests, the largest error occurred in the 4th test, with a coordinate error of 41.8mm. The least error occurred in the 3rd test with a coordinate error of 12.1mm. Also, negative displacement error was found only in the Y axis.

Figure 10: Coordinate testing of Robot Arm

3.2. Object Detection Accuracy

The objective of this test was to evaluate the accuracy of the Sonar sensor in detecting the distance of various objects positioned at different angles and distances. The measurement was carried out using a coordinate board, ruler, and protractor, following the same methodology as the previous test. **Table 1** shows the accuracy of distance measurement of objects placed perpendicular to the sensor module, while **Table 2** highlights the precision of distance measurement when objects are placed at an angle to the sensor. The obstacle detection accuracy test was modelled after a similar test conducted by A. Biswas et al. [13].

Table 1. Data Collection of Distance Measurement Accuracy

Object Type		Reference Distance(mm)			
		20	30	40	50
Rectangular Shape	Solid Object	19.19 (4.05%)	28.75 (4.17%)	38.98 (2.55%)	47.93 (4.14%)
	Semi-Transparent Object	20.15 (0.75%)	29.00 (3.33%)	-	47.92 (4.16%)
	Solid Object with Protrusions	19.82 (0.90%)	30.02 (0.07%)	38.52 (3.70%)	48.13 (3.74%)
Cylindrical Shape	Plastic Bottle	20.15 (0.75%)	28.99 (3.37%)	-	48.3 (3.40%)

From the data collected in **Table 1**, it is evident that the shape of the object does not influence distance measurement accuracy. In all cases, distance measurement remained consistent with some errors. However, as the object is placed further from the sensor, accuracy decreases considerably. For the sensor used, the testing data indicates the threshold to be approximately 50cm. Fields without testing data have been left blank.

Table 2. Data Collection of Angular Displacement Accuracy

Object Type	Angular Displacement		
	-10 Degree	0 Degree	10 Degree
Rectangular Shape	19.84 (0.80%)	18.87 (5.65%)	19.50 (2.50%)
Cylindrical Shape	20.15 (0.75%)	20.79 (3.95%)	20.47 (2.35%)
Spherical Shape	20.47 (2.35%)	18.89 (5.55%)	19.84 (0.80%)

From the data presented in **Table 2**, it is observed the sensor performs distance measurement reliably for angular placement of up to 10-degree tilt with the Sonar module with minimal error. However, for angular placements beyond this range, the measurement causes significant errors. As a result, data collected for angular placements beyond 10 degrees were excluded from further analysis and not included in **Table 2**.

4. RESULT

From the experiments conducted, the accuracy of Medibot's functionalities was validated. The coordinate testing of the robot arm proved its ability to reach any desired coordinate with negligible error. The tests carried out to measure object detection accuracy of the sonar system also showed reliable accuracy up to reasonable distance. This validated the claim of it being suitable to use for obstacle detection in autonomous navigation.

Moreover, the bot is affordable to produce and suitable for supplementing medical delivery services in underdeveloped regions. The cost breakdown of parts used to make Medibot is shown in **Table 3**. The total cost of component is only \$120, which makes it suitable for widespread implementation in underdeveloped regions. Additionally, during outbreaks, it can provide invaluable healthcare services while mitigating the transmission of diseases.

Table 3. Table of Prices for Components Used.

Component	Quantity	Cost (USD)
3D printed parts	-	33.49
Arduino Uno	1	7.53
Servo Motor (MG996R)	5	15.07
DC Motor	4	12.56
Motor Driver (L293D)	1	2.51
Buck Module	1	1.67
LiPo Battery	1	18.84
ESP32 Cam	1	6.28
Sonar Sensor	1	1.27
LCD Display (20x4)	1	3.35
Wheel Set (4)	1	3.35
PVC Sheet	-	5.74
Others	-	8.37
Total		120.03

5. CONCLUSION

Medibot proposes a promising solution to healthcare delivery challenges in underdeveloped regions, particularly during outbreaks of contagious diseases. By integrating semi-autonomous navigation, object manipulation capabilities, and interactive functionalities, Medibot is designed to address the gap in existing robotic healthcare solutions, which are often too expensive or complex for deployment in low-resource settings.

This robot's design prioritizes affordability, ease of operation, and adaptability, making it suitable for navigating through unplanned and narrow environments such as urban slums and rural areas. With its capability to transport medical supplies, collect patient samples, and facilitate remote communication between healthcare workers and patients, Medibot has the potential to significantly enhance healthcare accessibility in underserved regions.

The performance tests validated Medibot's accuracy in obstacle detection and navigation. It consistently achieved mean error of under 5% in measuring obstacle distances, regardless of shape or type of objects, ensuring reliable autonomous movement. The arm also demonstrated high precision in reaching target coordinates, with the largest mean error being under 2cm, enabling dependable pick and place operations by the arm. Future enhancements can further extend Medibot's capabilities and improve its efficiency. Additionally, Medibots' ability to maintain cost-effectiveness, as evidenced by its low production cost of \$120, makes it a feasible option for widespread implementation, even in resource-limited healthcare systems.

The performance and affordable cost make Medibot a viable alternative to the robot-based healthcare solutions available in the market. Due to its lower cost compared to the available solutions, its implementation can be more widespread. While the compact and small shape enables its deployment in slum areas with narrow roads and unplanned establishments. Moreover, its versatile functionalities make it a suitable candidate for remote nursing and medical care delivery service.

However, improvements can be made in several key areas. Object gripping capabilities can be enhanced by integrating a piezoelectric sensor into the end effector. This sensor would assist in securely holding the object and provide information about its geometry. Implementation of a 3D sonar system can greatly increase the range and accuracy of obstacle detection. It will also enable the detection of inclined surfaces, pits, and bumps. Limitations of Arduino platform not supporting Machine Learning algorithms led to no implementation of Object Detection. Using a Raspberry Pi can resolve this limitation. Greater precision in arm movement can be achieved by using higher quality metal servo motors and more tight tolerance 3D printed parts. Additionally, careful consideration of various linkage and components' geometry and mass can reduce vibrations during arm movements, allowing for smoother operation and increased load-bearing capacity. Lastly, incorporating AI based technologies can further improve accuracy and precision of its functionalities.

Further research into Medibot can shape it into a dependable assistant in the healthcare delivery sector. Expanding its applicability in diverse medical contexts, Medibot can become a crucial tool in improving healthcare access in marginalized communities, reducing disease transmission during outbreaks, and addressing the growing demand for healthcare services in underdeveloped regions.

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